

FREQUENCY STEERING OF HYDROGEN MASERS

Lee A. Breakiron and Paul Koppang

Directorate of Time
U.S. Naval Observatory
Washington, DC 20392

Abstract

The two Master Clock (MC) systems at USNO are steered in frequency so as to equalize their times with that of a mean timescale produced by an ensemble of hydrogen masers and cesium standards weighted dynamically and revised by post-processing. Occasional steers are also made to keep UTC (USNO) close to TAI. Experiments have been made with different steering algorithms in a search for an optimal one, i.e. that equalizes the times of an MC and the mean timescale satisfactorily closely and quickly without destabilizing the MC's maser to an extent noticeable by our users. Such a choice appears to be one wherein 10 or 90 days of data are averaged to determine the MC's frequency, a damping factor (time constant) of 100 days is employed in the time equalization, and an upper limit of 3.5 parts in 10^{15} is set on the maximum daily frequency change. An algorithm utilizing linear quadratic Gaussian control of Kalman-filtered data is being tested on one MC. The absolute frequency stability of UTC (USNO) appears to be comparable to that of TAI. A back-up USNO MC has been established at Falcon AFB, CO.

INTRODUCTION

In order to disseminate time and provide real-time monitoring of other timing systems, USNO maintains a Master Clock (MC) system consisting of two or more hydrogen masers that are steered in frequency to keep their time close to that of a mean ("paper") timescale produced by an ensemble of cesium clocks (mainly HP5071s) and hydrogen masers. Additional, smaller steers are occasionally made to keep the Master Clocks close to TAI. Some of these recent corrections have incorporated the black-body corrections to TAI recommended by the CCDS [1]. In order to provide precise time commensurate with the increasing demands of our users, different methods of steering the MCs have been investigated in a search for an optimal strategy.

THE USNO CLOCK ENSEMBLE

The ensemble presently consists of 12 hydrogen masers and 45 cesium-beam atomic clocks in 14 environmental chambers. In particular, the two MCs have recently been relocated to new chambers whose temperature is controlled to within 0.2 deg C and relative humidity to within 0.5%. Reliability is virtually guaranteed by physical separation of the clocks, generator-backup power supplies, and time signal and environmental alarms and monitoring computer programs. About 89% of the clocks are weighted in the mean timescale computation at any one time.

Hewlett-Packard model 5071A clocks have been replacing the older 5061A and 5061B models; the ratio is now at 90%. HP5071As have demonstrated an improvement of more than an order of magnitude in both accuracy and in environmental insensitivity over previous commercial clocks [2]. Automatically cavity-tuned Sigma Tau masers (now numbering 9) have been replacing SAO masers (now 3). Cavity-tuned masers have outstanding short-term stability, excellent intermediate-term stability, and comparatively low frequency drifts. Together, these new types of cesium and maser frequency standards place stringent demands on steering a clock's frequency toward their mean; a mean timescale computed from their data can have a stability of a couple parts in 10^{15} for a sampling time of from 1,000 seconds to about a year.

USNO MEAN TIMESCALE COMPUTATION

USNO clock times relative to the MCs are measured hourly. The clock frequencies and drifts are determined over periods of at least 90 days and are averaged by a mean timescale algorithm that weights the clocks based on the clock-type class average of their frequency stability. In particular, the masers are weighted much more than the cesiums in the recent past, but are gradually phased out over 75 days. Since the MCs are steered toward the mean timescale as predicted from the recent past, the masers, whose stability is greatest in the short-term (hours to days), determine the short-term stability of both the mean timescale and the MCs, while the cesiums, whose stability is greatest on the long-term (weeks to months), determine the long-term stability of both. To put it another way, the masers determine the stability of UTC (USNO), while the cesiums (being the standards for frequency) determine its accuracy. Refinement of these weights by use of individual Allan variances is under test. Any significant change in a clock's behavior immediately precipitates deweighting and re-evaluation. Because of the dynamic weighting of the masers, the entire timescale is recomputed every hour, permitting revision of the mean retroactively as data accumulate and knowledge of the clock frequencies and drifts improves, and providing all the benefits of both a real-time and a postprocessed timescale [3,4].

Individual physical clocks may fail, so for redundancy, at least two MCs are kept in continuous operation at USNO. Also, an off-site back-up MC and ensemble were relocated from Richmond, FL to Falcon AFB, CO in Apr 1996. The latter is called the Alternate Master Clock (AMC) and is the reference for an ensemble currently consisting of two Sigma Tau masers and eight HP5071A cesiums; eventually it will consist of three masers and 12 cesiums.

FREQUENCY STEERING OF THE MASTER CLOCKS

At USNO, the two MCs are each steered toward a mean timescale computed from differences between the ensemble clocks and the respective MC. Since the timescales should be identical, this procedure keeps the MCs close together in case one should fail, while preserving their independence. Ideally a third reference should be available for voting between them in order to determine the culprit clock in the case of a phase excursion, but a real-time mean timescale can serve this function, as can the AMC; USNO has had a third MC in the past and plans to have one again. The MCs and AMC are generally kept within 10 ns in time and one part in 10^{14} in frequency of one another; a maser can be calibrated even more closely if a physical substitution is required for one of the MCs. MC #2 is the source of real-time UTC (USNO).

Generally, an MC is the best clock on site; masers replaced cesiums in this role at USNO in 1984. The MC's output is controlled by small, predetermined time steps by means of a phase microstepper or frequency steps by means of a frequency synthesizer. Use of phase microsteppers at USNO was abandoned in 1991 because of the added noise they incurred.

Unfortunately, the subsequent use of each maser's internal frequency synthesizer for steering did not provide access to an unsteered signal, so the steered signal had to mathematically de-steered before the data could be provided to the BIPM and weighted in our mean timescale computation. The recent installation of Sigma Tau Auxiliary Output Generators (external frequency synthesizers) at USNO and the AMC again makes possible access to the masers' unsteered signals.

Keeping any precise clock to within about 10 nanoseconds of a paper timescale is challenging for several reasons. Any physical steering of a clock will inevitably degrade its frequency stability at around the same sampling time that it is steered. At the least, such frequency corrections should be smaller than the frequency fluctuations inherent in the clock and timescale. In particular, steering that is too rapid will cause overshoot and oscillation about the target timescale [5], unless one designs a very aggressive, critically damped control algorithm. Frequency changes that are too large will be obvious to the user, to whom frequency stability is often more important than exact time. Yet the steering must be able to handle any frequency excursions by the clock. And the mean timescale itself is noisy and is jolted by any changes in ensemble make-up and in clock frequencies and weights. The frequent recomputation of the USNO timescale, though, does reduce some of the noise in the predicted steering target. Still, the need to adjust the MC's time by steering its frequency may degrade its frequency stability.

For this reason, it is not desirable to steer by too large an amount at any one time. Also, the smaller a steer needs to be, the fewer the consequences if it fails to be made through some malfunction. For example, if the MC's frequency is kept close to that of the target, a loss of control will not result in a large excursion of the clock's phase. Contrarily but less importantly, fewer steers are better than many, at least above some level (unless there is a high drift relative to the target). And the fewer the steers, the less the opportunity for malfunctions.

In order to estimate how much the steering degraded maser performance, the frequency stability of Sigma Tau masers NAV2, NAV3, and NAV8 and SAO masers P-18 and P-19 were examined before and after they were steered. The degradation did not exceed 2.0 parts in 10^{15} , at least for

the gentle steering rate employed (≤ 4.6 parts in 10^{15} in a day). Of course, if the steering rate is too gentle, the destabilization may be negligible, but the steering target may not be approached sufficiently closely or quickly. Again, this is a matter of output control, rather than intrinsic noise.

The steering correction to each MC's frequency is applied daily at 13 UT. It consists of:

$$\Delta f_{\text{target-MC}}/F_f + t_{\text{target-MC}}/(8.64 \cdot 10^{13} F_i) + \Delta f_b$$

where

$\Delta f_{\text{target-MC}}$ = target frequency relative to the MC at the time of the steer, corrected for drift

F_f = damping factor applied to the frequency difference correction

$t_{\text{target-MC}}$ = time difference in ns between the target and the MC

F_i = damping factor applied to the time difference correction = time constant in days

Δf_b = frequency bias to steer the MC's time toward a secondary target (*e.g.* TAI)

all predicted for the time of the steer. Usually, and in this paper, the target is the mean timescale.

Such a frequency correction requires that the frequency of the MC be predictable and, hence, that its frequency and drift be known accurately, which entails averaging first differences between time intervals in the white FM noise region (in our case, hourly) over a period of time sufficiently long to determine them accurately, but not long enough for them to vary significantly. Any time and frequency steps must be removed mathematically. In particular, the effect of the daily steering on the MC itself must be corrected for when averaging over more than the previous day.

Prediction of the steering target is complicated by USNO's obligation to keep UTC (USNO) within 100 ns of UTC (BIPM) (= TAI + leap seconds), as was recommended for all major UTC references by the CCDS at its 12th meeting in 1993.

Time used to be received from BIPM 45 days or more after the fact, so the USNO timescale had to be used to extrapolate TAI at least this far into the future. Over the past year, this delay has been reduced to about 8 days by an admirable effort on the part of BIPM, which has made our steering toward TAI a lot more precise. Our predictions of TAI are based on the last 180 days of data from BIPM's monthly Circular T report (and supplementary faxes) and are determined from a linear least-squares solution for frequency and drift of the first differences between TAI and USNO's unsteered mean timescale. This assumes that the dominant noise is white FM noise. The error of the predicted TAI is about ± 10 ns. Steering corrections toward TAI are limited to small (1.0 part in 10^{15}) frequency adjustments no more often than about once a month [6]. The USNO prediction algorithm has been shown to be very close to optimal [2].

COMPARISON OF STEERING TECHNIQUES

USNO has been testing several different maser steering algorithms in a search for an optimal one capable of correcting a MC's frequency and time to that of its target at rate fast enough to deal with any drifts or excursions, but not so fast

that our users can detect the steers. Most of these algorithms involve varying the damping factors above, the interval over which the frequency of the MC is determined, and an upper limit on the size of the daily frequency steer. The damping factors reduce both the shock to the MC and the noise introduced by steering toward a moving target, which the mean timescale effectively is because of the fluctuations in its real-time determination mentioned above and illustrated in Fig. 1. Because the mean timescale in its latest hours is based heavily on masers, this damping may somewhat degrade the MC's time and frequency accuracy, but it also reduces the effect of a dropout from the weighted ensemble of one of these masers and, hence, is a tradeoff made to ensure longer-term stability.

Among the algorithms tested were those involving: (1) frequency averaging interval of either 1, 10, or 90 days; (2) a frequency change damping factor of either 1 or 5; (3) a time change damping factor of either 50 or 100; and (4) a maximum daily frequency steer of either 3.5 or 4.6 parts in 10^{15} . In one case the steers themselves were filtered by averaging them over 10 days. Drift was taken into account when significant (> 3.5 parts in 10^{17} /day). The masers tested were NAV8 = MC #1, NAV3 = MC #2, P-18, and P-19 relative to the unsteered reference masers NAV4 and NAV5. From 83 to 183 days of data per maser were employed, and were robustly filtered by: (1) first rejecting first differences whose absolute values were > 5 times the median of the absolute deviations of the first differences from their own median; and (2) further rejecting first differences whose absolute values were > 2 times their standard deviation.

All the algorithms were successful in attaining the targets in a reasonable time, as can be seen in Figs. 2, 3, and 4, where the phases are plotted relative to a common end point, DAMP is the damping factor, and MFC is the maximum frequency change in parts in 10^{15} . In Fig. 2, 1 day of frequency data was

averaged; in Fig. 3, 10 days; and in Fig. 4, 10 days (maser P-18) or 90 days (masers P-19 and NAV8).

This leaves maximum frequency stability (the lowest Allan deviation) as the criterion for choice. Selected results of the frequency stability analysis are given in Figs. 5, 6, and 7, where τ is the sampling time and maser NAV5 was the reference (though the noise at small τ is virtually all from the measurement system). The most successful algorithms in this regard involved frequency averaging over either 10 or 90 days, a frequency damping factor of 1, a time damping factor of 100, and a maximum daily frequency steer of 3.5 parts in 10^{15} /day (i.e. the lowest curve in Figs. 6 and 7). Averaging over more than one day not only reduces the measurement noise, but allows the steering to take more advantage of the postprocessed timescale.

Setting an upper limit on the frequency change might reduce a MC's stability in the case of a phase excursion by the MC, so such excursions must be checked for and corrected on an *ad hoc* basis.

ONGOING TEST OF A NEW STEERING TECHNIQUE

An alternative but closely related method of generating a mean timescale, rather than that used above, is through the use of a Kalman filter (e.g. [7]). MC #1 and the AMC are currently being steered hourly by an experimental method utilizing linear quadratic Gaussian (LQG) control that makes use of a Kalman filter, recently proposed by Koppang and Leland [8]. The AMC is linked to USNO via Two-Way Satellite Time Transfer and GPS timing receivers. The AMC's two MCs are being steered to USNO's MC #2, but in case of failure of the USNO MCs, they can be steered to the AMC

FIG. 1. REAL-TIME VS. POSTPROCESSED MEAN TIMESCALE

FIG. 2. TIME DIFFERENCE (MABER NAV8 - END POINT)

FIG. 3. TIME DIFFERENCE (MABER NAV3 - END POINT)

FIG. 4. TIME DIFFERENCE (MASER - ENDPOINT)

FIG. 5. FREQUENCY STABILITY OF MASER NAV8 VS. NAV6

FIG. 6. FREQUENCY STABILITY OF MASER NAV3 VS. NAV5

FIG. 7. FREQUENCY STABILITY OF MASERS VS. NAV5

mean timescale, which itself is being steered to the USNO mean timescale.

In the LQG method, the Kalman filter estimates a state vector which is used as input for a control calculation. One solves for:

$$u(k) = \text{fractional frequency change of the synthesizer} \\ = -\hat{G}_o \hat{x}(k)$$

where:

$$\hat{x}(k) = \text{estimate of } \begin{bmatrix} x_{MC} - x_{mean} \\ y_{MC} - y_{mean} \end{bmatrix}$$

x = phase difference in seconds

y = fractional frequency difference

and the gain \hat{G}_o is given by:

$$\hat{G}_o = (B^T \hat{k}_o B + W_R)^{-1} B^T \hat{k}_o \Phi$$

where $B = \begin{bmatrix} \tau \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$, τ = interval between steers, \hat{k}_o is a solution to the steady-state Ricatti equation:

$$\hat{k}_o = \Phi^T \hat{k}_o \Phi + W_Q - \Phi^T \hat{k}_o B (B^T \hat{k}_o B + W_R)^{-1} B^T \hat{k}_o \Phi,$$

and Φ = transition matrix = $\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tau \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$.

W_Q and W_R are matrices chosen so that their relative sizes provide the desired balance between the steering effort and the deviation from the target time and frequency. Using simulations, Koppang and Leland found that:

$$\hat{G}_o = \begin{bmatrix} 3.3185 \cdot 10^{-8} & 0.014976 \end{bmatrix}$$

assuming reasonably quick steering of one maser to another

without being so quick that the stability of the steered maser was significantly degraded.

We used the same value of the gain \hat{G}_o to actually steer USNO maser NAV8 to the USNO mean timescale. The exceptional control afforded by this method is demonstrated in Fig. 8, in which a 7-ns offset is steered out in a month. Preliminary results show that the frequency stability is not as good as that of most of the other algorithms studied (see Fig. 9), but adjustments in some of the parameters, such as reducing the gain, should improve this. This gain reduction is necessary because the gain in [8] was based on a postprocessed, rather than a real-time, mean. Recalculating the gain with different W_Q and W_R matrices is analogous to adjusting the damping factor in the above algorithms.

We can also compare the input to and output from the AOG downstream from the maser to evaluate the degree of frequency destabilization due to the steering (see Fig. 10) without the noise contributed by the reference maser (hence the low Allan deviations at small τ). Again, the resulting destabilization is no worse than 2 parts in 10^{15} at 1 day.

ABSOLUTE FREQUENCY STABILITY OF TIMESCALES

UTC (USNO) has been within 15 ns of TAI (averaging 7 ns) since Apr 1995. Both UTC (USNO) and TAI have been improving with time, due primarily to the increase in the number of clocks in their ensembles and to the introduction of HP5071A cesiums and hydrogen masers, but also to improvements in clock environments, measurement systems, data links, mean timescale and steering algorithms, clock weighting schemes, and filtering. This steady improvement may be seen in Fig. 11, which shows the relative frequency stability of UTC

FIG. 8. PHASE OF MASER NAV8 VS. USNO MEAN TIMESCALE

FIG. 9. FREQUENCY STABILITY OF MASER NAV8 VS. NAV6

FIG. 10. FREQUENCY STABILITY OF STEERED VS. UNSTEERED MASER

(USNO) and EAL, the unsteered version of TAI. Each curve is for one year's data, from the middle of one year to the middle of the next. The two timescales are correlated, because USNO currently contributes 39% of the clock weight to TAI, so both must be improving. However, the current absolute stability of UTC (USNO) alone is probably only somewhat worse than the lowest curve, because division by the square root of two (assuming the two timescales are independent and are of equal stability) is almost cancelled out by the factor $1/(1 - 39\%)$ which approximately corrects the stability of UTC (USNO) for the correlation between the two timescales [2].

Just how stable are these and other individual timescales? We may determine this by performing an n-cornered-hat solution [9] among an independent set of the best timescales available, e.g. UTC (USNO), UTC (NIST), UTC (PTB), and UTC (SU) [10], and then compute the stability of TAI from TAI's stability relative to the one of these possessing a low weight in the computation of (and, hence, probably a low correlation with) TAI, e.g. UTC (SU). This procedure will be successful only if the stability of each timescale is reasonably constant with time. The stabilities of all these timescales, though, have been improving over the years. Also, UTC (SU) suffered a significant frequency change on MJD 49799. Consequently, we will restrict the solution to the 430 days available since MJD 49799.

The results are shown in Fig. 12 (where the error bars have been tipped to avoid overlapping). In particular, the frequency stabilities of UTC (USNO) and TAI are similar, in spite of the fact that TAI is based on about 175 weighted clocks and UTC (USNO) is based on about 50 clocks included in the former. This fact is presumably due to differences in the relative degrees of homogeneity of the respective clock ensembles, the degree of the optimality of the respective mean

timescale algorithms and weighting schemes, and the higher data rate.

The absolute frequency stabilities of both UTC (USNO) and TAI can be seen from the Figure to attain 2.9 parts in 10^{15} for a sampling time of 80 days ($\log \tau = 6.84$). In the same interval, the Allan deviation of UTC (USNO) relative to the USNO mean timescale was 9.1 parts in 10^{16} for the same τ .

UTC (USNO) has been steered mainly toward the USNO mean timescale, rather than mainly toward TAI, because of instabilities in TAI and delays in receiving it that are now largely things of the past. Consequently, there might seem to be a dilemma as to whether USNO's mean timescale or TAI might make the better primary target for steering. However, if the two can be kept close together, as they are now, there should be no need for conflict.

UTC (USNO) is accessible through GPS and our Automated Data Service (ADS). USNO's prediction of real-time TAI may be accessed on our ADS (under command "astro/bipmx"). The ADS is accessible on the Internet: (1) via telnet at tycho.usno.navy.mil, logging in as "ads"; (2) on the World Wide Web at <http://tycho.usno.navy.mil>; and (3) via ftp at tycho.usno.navy.mil, logging in as "anonymous."

Besides USNO's mean timescale that is occasionally steered toward TAI, USNO also computes an unsteered mean timescale "A.1," mostly for internal use (e.g. evaluating the frequencies of our clocks). This timescale is available in BIPM's Circulars T, but making it more readily available would only expose others to the changing differences between the real-time and postprocessed mean timescales. The latest Circular T, as well as past values of TAI - UTC (USNO), are also available on USNO's ADS.

FIG. 11. FREQUENCY STABILITY OF UTC (USNO) VS. EAL

CONCLUSIONS

Of the steering algorithms tested, the most successful ones were those that averaged either 10 or 90 days of data to determine the MC's frequency, employed a damping factor of 100 days in the time equalization, and set an upper limit of 3.5 parts in 10^{15} on the maximum daily frequency change. The algorithm averaging 10 days of data will continue to be used on MC #2, the source of real-time UTC (USNO).

MC #1 will continue to be steered by an experimental algorithm utilizing linear quadratic Gaussian control using Kalman filter theory until it has been fully evaluated. Ultimately both MCs will be steered by the same algorithm to ensure their time and frequency proximity to one another. A new measurement system now being tested at AMC will reduce our short-term measurement noise at both USNO and the AMC.

The absolute frequency stability of both UTC (USNO) and TAI attains 3 parts in 10^{15} in about 3 months. A real-time estimate of TAI is available from USNO.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Thomas, "Report of the BIPM Time Section 1993-1995," presented at 13th Meeting of the Comité Consultatif pour la Définition de la Seconde, Paris, 1996.
- [2] D.W. Allan, "Tutorial: Clock and clock systems performance measures," *Proceedings of the 27th Annual Precise Time and Time Interval (PTTI) Applications and Planning Meeting*, San Diego, California, 29 Nov-1 Dec 1995, NASA CP-3334, pp. 209-234.
- [3] L.A. Breakiron, "Timescale algorithms combining cesium clocks and hydrogen masers," *Proceedings of the 23rd*

Annual Precise Time and Time Interval (PTTI) Applications and Planning Meeting, Pasadena, California, 3-5 Dec 1991, NASA CP-3159, pp. 297-305.

- [4] L.A. Breakiron, "The effects of clock errors on timescale stability," *Proceedings of the 26th Annual Precise Time and Time Interval (PTTI) Applications and Planning*, Reston, Virginia, 6-8 Dec 1994, NASA CP-3302, pp. 369-380.
- [5] H. Chadsey, "Methodologies for steering clocks," *Proceedings of the 26th Annual Precise Time and Time Interval (PTTI) Applications and Planning Meeting*, Reston, Virginia, 6-8 Dec 1994, pp. 351-368.
- [6] M. Miranian, "UTC dissemination to the real-time user: the role of USNO," *Proceedings of the 27th Annual Precise Time and Time Interval (PTTI) Applications and Planning Meeting*, San Diego, California, 29 Nov-1 Dec 1995, NASA CP-3334, pp. 75-86.
- [7] J.A. Barnes and D.W. Allan, "Time scale stabilities based on time and frequency Kalman filters," *Proceedings of the 39th Annual Symposium on Frequency Control*, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, 29-31 May 1985, pp. 107-112.
- [8] P. Koppang and R. Leland, "Steering of frequency standards by the use of linear quadratic Gaussian control theory," *Proceedings of the 27th Annual Precise Time and Time Interval (PTTI) Applications and Planning Meeting*, San Diego, California, 29 Nov-1 Dec 1995, NASA CP-3334, pp. 257-268.
- [9] D.W. Allan, "Time and frequency (time-domain) characterization, estimation, and prediction of precision clocks and oscillators," *IEEE Transactions on Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics, and Frequency Control*, UFFC-34, pp. 647-654, November 1987.

- [10] Annual Reports of the BIPM Time Section, Bureau International des Poids et Mesures, Sevres, France.

FIG. 12. FREQUENCY STABILITY OF INDIVIDUAL TIMESCALES

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank Dr. Jacques Azoubib of BIPM for data regarding TAI.